

Genomics (1/3)

Services	Internal
Quality Control	
Tapestation €/sample	4,70
Fragment analyzer €/per run (11 samples)	26,14
DNA Library Preparation	
Nextera €/sample	20,08
DNA-MGI €/sample	20,08
DNA-NEB €/sample	20,08
Nanopore Rapid Barcoding €/up to 24 samples	131,05
Nanopore Ligation €/sample	131,05
RNA Library Preparation	
SmartSeq Cells / RNA total – step 1 €/sample	17,03
SmartSeq – step 2 €/sample	20,08
RNA Ribodepletion €/sample	53,38
Library Preparation - Metabarcoding	
Illumina 18S/ITS/16S €/sample	8,73

Genomics (2/3)

Services		Internal
Spatial Transcriptomics		
Stomics - FreshFrozen	€/slide	1623,63
Stomics - FFPE	€/slide	1623,63
Visium HD – Probe Panel (Human/Mouse)		*
Visium HD – WT 3' Gene Expression		*
Single Cell		
10X GEM-X kit Single Cell 3' / 5'	€/sample	1208,56
10X GEM-X chip Single Cell 3' / 5'	€/chip	278,74
10X GEM-X kit Single Cell Feature Barcode	€/sample	53,43
10X GEM-X Single Cell 5' V(D)J	€/sample	114,88
10X GEM-X Universal 3'/5' Gene Expression OCM	€/up to 4 samples	1367,64
10X GEM-X 3'/5' chip OCM	€/chip	268,82
10X GEM-X Flex v2	€/sample	1208,56
10X GEM-X Flex v2 chip	€/chip	278,74
10X Next-Gem EPI ATAC	€/sample	1367,64
10X Next-Gem EPI ATAC chip	€/chip	278,74
MGI DNBeLab	€/sample	278,74

* No internal billing, reagent kit charged directly to research project but managed by platform

Genomics (3/3)

Services		Internal
Single cell machine		
Chromium X – equipment only (reagents by lab and after training and authorization by platform)	€/run	16,60
Sequencing		
Illumina NextSeq 2000 – 100 cycles	€/Gbp	30,29
Illumina NextSeq 2000 – 200 cycles	€/Gbp	16,60
Illumina NextSeq 2000 – 300 cycles	€/Gbp	17,36
Illumina NextSeq 2000 – 600 cycles	€/Gbp	16,60
Nanopore MinION	€/flow cell	399,03
Nanopore PromethION	€/flow cell	590,57
MGI G400 FCL SE 100	€/full run	1008,09
MGI G400 DB FCS SE 100	€/full run	590,57
MGI G400 DB FCS PE 150	€/full run	1008,09
MGI G400 DB FCL PE 150	€/full run	1008,09
MGI G400 Stomics	€/full run	1008,09

In situations of high technical complexity, the amounts invoiced will be determined based on the records of services actually provided, as evidenced by scheduling systems and/or technical reports validated by the responsible units.

